

WORLD CLIMATE
RESEARCH PROGRAMME
**OPEN SCIENCE
CONFERENCE**
23 - 27 OCT. 2023 | RWANDA

CMIP and CORDEX evaluation and analysis tools

EVENT REPORT

Bibliographic Information

This report should be cited as: Nasser, A., Reboita, M., Lake, L., and Nilsson, L. (2024), *CMIP and CORDEX evaluation and analysis tools: Report from WCRP Open Science Conference 2023*. doi:10.5281/zenodo.10619796.

Disclaimer

The designations employed in the WCRP Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) or Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX), publications and the presentation of material in this publication do not imply the expression of any opinion whatsoever on the part of CMIP, CORDEX, the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) – including its Sponsor Organizations the World Meteorological Organization (WMO), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO and the International Science Council (ISC) – the European Space Agency (ESA) in its role as host organisation of the CMIP International Project Office (CMIP-IPO), or the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI) in its role as host organisation of the CORDEX IPO concerning the legal status of any country, territory, city or area or of its authorities, or concerning the delimitation of its frontiers or boundaries.

The findings, interpretations and conclusions expressed in CMIP and CORDEX publications with named authors are those of the authors alone and do not necessarily reflect those of CMIP, CORDEX WCRP, its Sponsor Organizations, SMHI, ESA or of their Members.

This document is not an official publication of the WCRP and has been issued without formal editing.

The views expressed herein do not necessarily have the endorsement of WCRP or its Members.

Any potential mention of specific companies or products does not imply that they are endorsed or recommended in preference to others of a similar nature which are not mentioned or advertised.

Copyright notice

This report is published by the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>) and thereunder made available for reuse for any purpose, subject to the license's terms, including proper attribution.

Acknowledgements

The report was written and edited by the staff of the CORDEX International Project Office (IPO), who are hosted by SMHI. We would like to thank all colleagues who contributed to this report.

ipoc@cordex.org
cmip-ipo@esa.int

CMIP and CORDEX Analysis and Evaluation Tools - Side Event Report

The session, which took place on the 23 November 2023 at the WCRP Open Science Conference in Rwanda, provided a showcase of tools that can be used for CMIP and CORDEX analysis and evaluation, along with demonstrating their main uses, advantages, and limitations.

The session, which was co-convened by the WCRP CMIP and CORDEX International Project Offices, began with welcoming the speakers and the participants, and a demonstration of the run-of-show was presented to the participants.

The side event was divided into 4 main sections:

1- Introduction to CMIP and CORDEX by Beth Dingley and Grigory Nikulin and demonstration of the aim of the event by Eleanor O'Rourke.

2- Pitch presentations on various tools, to help the participants decide which tool they are interested in and to foster further discussions in the third section. Besides the tools that were demoed and discussed at tables there were also online pitches on cloud platforms such as Pangeo, NOAA and XMIP by Aparna Radhakrishnan and Julius Busecke. Some feed-back on tools from a workshop in Niamey was presented by Nana Ama Browne Klutse and we got insight on experiences on tools for CMIP and CORDEX from Giresse Turin.

3- Table discussion on specific tools.

4- Wrap up with reporting from demo tables and key take home messages

The discussions in each table can be summarized as follows:

Table 1: [CAVA analytics](#)

Participants were interactive, and most of them were coders. Olivier Crespo, University of Cape Town, gave a demonstration of the tool Climate and Agriculture Risk Visualization and Assessment (CAVA) and showcased some aspects of it with the participants.

The Q&A of this table covered the ability to download specific geographical data, the programming language used (R), available variables, and the existence of tutorials. The expert affirmed the tool's flexibility in choosing coordinates or countries for data download as well as the availability of tutorials explaining variables and functions. Additional queries focused on dataset ranges and data pre-processing. One coder expressed the opinion that the tool simplifies task execution.

Table 2: [CORDEX](#)

Participants were very interactive in this group and wanted to learn more about CORDEX which was presented by Grigory Nikulin, Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute

(SMHI). A summary of the table discussion is provided below with the first discussion being the explanation about what CORDEX is,

- CORDEX, a WCRP program, aims to guide and establish protocols for regional climate models (RCMs), supporting users globally. Its goals include understanding local climate phenomena, improving RCMs, producing coordinated downscaled projections and fostering knowledge exchange with users.
- CORDEX-CMIP6 advances since CMIP5 include aerosol incorporation, improved physics, higher resolution, new scenarios with socio-economic developments (SSPs), and increased data availability (more vertical levels and hourly frequencies).
- The RCMs for CORDEX-CMIP6 include RegCM, REMO, RACMO, WRF, HELIN, ALADIN, ICON, and CCLM.
- These models will not be downscaled for all domains in the first round of simulations.
- The resolution varies by domain, e.g., 25 km for some domains and around 10 km for Europe.
- The experiment design protocol for CORDEX-CMIP6 is ready since 2022, using ERA5 as boundary conditions for the evaluation runs.
- The number of CMIP6-GCMs driving RCMs will vary between domains and institutions.
- Projections focus on scenarios SSP1-2.6 (low impact) and SSP3-7.0 (high impact) initially. Additional downscaling is recommended for SSP2-4.5 and also SSP5-8.5, considering extreme scenarios.
- The protocol link for CORDEX-CMIP6 simulations is https://cordex.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/CORDEX-CMIP6_exp_design_RCM.pdf.
- The community's preference is to span lower and higher impact scenarios rather than intermediate ones.
- RCMs downscaled simulations for CMIP6 are not yet complete, and users can check the status at <https://wcrp-cordex.github.io/simulation-status/>.

Table 3: [IPCC WGI Interactive Atlas](#)

Richard Jones, UK Met Office, presented the IPCC WGI Interactive Atlas and it attracted mainly the new users of this tool. Most of the discussions were about the following points:

- The available scenarios in the tool.
- The possibility of downloading data over a certain area with a certain time span.
- The resolution of the available datasets.
- The available variables

Table 4: [ESMValTool](#)

At this table, [Birgit Hassler](#), German Aerospace Center (DLR), and Forrest Hoffman, Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL), presented ESMValTool. Some of the participants were aware of the tool, but most of them were beginners at using it, while some others did not know about it before the session. The participants were interested to learn more about the features of this tool. Here is a summary of the discussion:

- ESMValTool is an interface for users to access CMIP and CORDEX projections, providing data pre-processing and post-processing functionalities. A new video presenting ESMValTool was launched at the event, and can be found at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sidM4EB6Sbo>
- The repository includes CMIP3 and CMIP5 data in NetCDF format.
- Documentation and tutorials are available for users. Selecting the appropriate tool depends on the user's specific needs, with ongoing efforts to publish a review article on available tools.
- A new gallery showcases model evaluation and benchmarking tools, accessible from the CMIP website at <https://wcrp-cmip.org/tools/model-benchmarking-and-evaluation-tools/>.
- The difference between evaluation and benchmarking was clarified: Evaluation is an assessment of model output in comparison with observational data, while benchmarking combines evaluation results to quantify and rank behavior of multiple models.
- Observation data can be downloaded automatically, and efforts are underway to transform point measurements into gridded data. Models can be run from laptops using the Linux operating system, and pre-processing functions are available, though unit conversion is recommended before this step.

Table 5: [Copernicus Climate Data Store and C3S](#)

[Carlo Buontempo](#), European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), presented the tool. Most of the participants were well-aware of Copernicus services, although

some did not know that there is an open access Copernicus tool for climate change scenarios as well as CMIP and CORDEX data. The participants were very interested to learn more about this tool.

Some of the participants found the tool easy to use.

Most of the questions were on the availability of certain regions and certain data ranges, and how the results are presented.

Table 6: [Climate Information Portal](#)

[Bode Gbobaniyi](#) demonstrated and discussed the tool. Some of the participants were aware of the tool, while others did not know about it before the session. The discussions were rich and most of them were on the following points:

- The availability of guides/tutorials.
- How can this tool help the researcher to further decide the following:
 - The suitable tool to use for a specific task/study.
 - The settings that are needed to be pre-selected to use each tool, such as location, emission scenarios, etc.
 - The different options and features each tool offers.

Pitch Spot 7: [CMIP model selection for downscaling](#)

[Stefan Sobolowski](#), Norwegian Research Centre (NORCE)/EURO-CORDEX, presented and discussed this tool. Participants showed high interest in it. Most of the participants were mid-level model users. Most of the discussions were about the following points:

- The code can be reproduced from peer reviewed papers if so desired.
- There was an interest in ocean parameters, other than the SST.
- There was also an interest in downscaling methods and the models providing boundary conditions for the downscaling.
- High-resolution tools.
- It is important to be careful when choosing to use multiple models together - they need to belong to the same family of models.
- A participant interested in oceanography mentioned that it is very good to find a tool that compares between models, especially the high-resolution models, so the user does not waste time over losing trials of using non-suitable models.
- The tool is suitable for comparing the results when using different models for a certain region.
- There is documentation available for the tool.
- The expert mentioned a white paper available for the tool.

Open Discussion

- Some of the tools were well-known to the participants, while others were not before the sessions.
- Most of the participants, especially from Global South, shared some difficulties while doing their research, such as:
 - Not being able to find support in getting started with new toolkits.
 - Not having enough resources, such as cloud computing resources, due to connectivity and bandwidth limitations
- A question arose on whether there is an intention to integrate some of the tools together in the future. A help can be the new CMIP Tools Database, which gives an overview of multiple tools. This helps users select the most useful tool for their purposes. The database can be accessed at www.wcrp-cmip.org/tools.
- Some tools may be easier than the others. However, documentation and tutorials are available. Moreover, some tool providers have monthly meetings to interact with users.
- In the end, one very important question is what these tools are made for. It is important to understand the tool and what the users need to do in their work before picking a certain tool to use.

Tools discussed at the OSC in Kigali

- General info on CORDEX and CMIP
- CAVA Analytics
- IPCC Interactive Atlas
- ESMValTools
- Copernicus Climate Data Store (CC Services)
- WMO/GCF/SMHI Climate Information Portal
- Model Benchmarking Tools for CMIP

- What is the purpose of the tools?
- Code for developing the tool – do you need to write your own code?
- Can cropping be done (country level etc)?
- Format of files?
- Tutorials?
- How to pick the most suitable tool?
- What are the differences between CMIP5/CORDEX and CMIP6/CORDEX?
- Difference between scenarios and reason for choice?
- Downscalings for all CORDEX domains?

- Downscaling methods?
- Models providing BC for downscaling?
- Available variables?
- Will old data (CMIP3 and 5) be available?
- Can observational data be downloaded?
- How do you run models (eg from laptops)?
- Selection of specific data ranges?
- Necessary settings for various tools?
- Tools for comparing regions and models
- High-resolution tools?

General Comments

- Many of the tools not so well-known – spread info!
- Specific Global South problems:
 - Find someone to help get started
 - Lacking resources (computers or could computing due to connectivity and bandwidth)
- Integrate tools in the future (like the CMIP dashboard)?
- Common tools for global, regional, local data!
- Documentation and tutorials!
- Meetings to interact with users
- Important to understand the tool and what it is made for to pick the right tool

Mainly three steps for tools

The speakers and organizers of the event in alphabetical order:

Nana Ama Browne Klutse	University of Ghana
Carlo Buontempo	ECMWF
Julius Busecke	Columbia University
Olivier Crespo	University of Cape Town
Elisabeth Dingley	CMIP International Project Office
Bode Gbobaniyi	CORDEX/SMHI
Forrest Hoffman	ORNL
Richard Jones	UK Met Office
Irène Lake	CORDEX/SMHI
Amira Nasser	Egyptian Meteorological Authority
Grigory Nikulin	CORDEX/SMHI
Lindha Nilsson	CORDEX/SMHI
Aparna Radhakrishanan	Princeton University
Michelle Reboita	Universidad de Itajubá (UNIFEI)
Eleanor O-Rourke	CMIP International Project Office
Stefan Sobolowski	NORCE/EURO-CORDEX
Giresse Turin	University of Yaoundé
Briony Turner	CMIP International Project Office

